

CERTIFICATE

Mónica Diana Salgueiro Faustino Sardo Belchior, Head of Academic Division of the Universidade NOVA de Lisboa - NOVA Medical School|Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, hereby CERTIFIES that **JORGE EMANUEL DA CRUZ MARTINS**, Citizen Card number 13071154, issued in Portugal, has successfully completed* the following Curricular Units of the **Integrated Master Degree in MEDICINE**:

Course	Acad. Year	Local Grade	Grade in Detail	Course Year	ECTS
Elective Clinical Rotation	2012/13	16	Sixteen	6	3
Surgery (Internship)	2012/13	14	Fourteen	6	---
Gynaecology and Obstetrics(Internship)	2012/13	18	Eighteen	6	---
Medicine (Internship)	2012/13	16	Sixteen	6	---
General Practice – Family Medicine (Internship)	2012/13	16	Sixteen	6	---
Pediatrics (Internship)	2012/13	18	Eighteen	6	---
Mental Health (Internship)	2012/13	17	Seventeen	6	---
Final Report	2012/13	18	Eighteen	6	---
Preparation clinical practice Internship	2012/13	16	Sixteen	6	3
	2012/13	17	Seventeen	6	54

(*The grading scale used at the NOVA Medical School|Faculdade de Ciências Médicas ranges from 0 to 20 (10 points is considered the threshold pass grade).

Universidade NOVA de Lisboa - NOVA Medical School|Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, on January 3, 2018.

Dra. Mónica Diana Salgueiro Faustino Sardo Belchior
Head of Academic Division

Certificate Tax: 12.30€

Urgent: 6.15€

Total: 18.45€

Conf. by: